

Determination of the effect of taekwondo training on liver enzymes and lipid metabolism of athletes

Determinación del efecto del entrenamiento de taekwondo sobre las enzimas hepáticas y el metabolismo lipídico de deportistas

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Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the changes in liver enzymes and lipid metabolism of athletes after ten-week taekwondo training. The research group consists of 26 male athletes who are licensed in taekwondo and take part in national level competitions. A training program was applied to the research group to improve their conditional characteristics with ninety-minute taekwondo exercises three days a week for ten weeks. Blood samples were taken from the athletes twice in the resting state, at the beginning and at the end of the training. In the samples taken from the research group, liver enzymes (ALP, AST, GGT, CRP, ALT, LDH), blood fats (HDL, LDL, cholesterol, triglyceride), glucose and urea levels were determined. The data were analyzed using the SPSS statistical package program. Significance level was accepted as $p < 0.05$. As a result of the research, it was observed that the liver enzyme values, GGT and LDH levels of the athletes increased in the pre-post test values, and there was a decrease in the levels of ALT, AST, ALP and CRP. It was determined that the glucose levels of the athletes increased in the pre-post test values, and there was a decrease in the pre-post test values of the urea levels. It was observed that the pre-post test values of HDL level, which is one of the lipid metabolism parameters of the research group, increased, and the pre-post test values for cholesterol, LDL and triglyceride levels decreased. In conclusion; It was observed that ten-week taekwondo trainings caused changes in the liver enzymes, blood fats, glucose and urea parameters of the athletes. In line with this information, we think that if training programs are organized considering the competition periods of the athletes, it will positively affect the performance of the athletes.

Keywords: Lipid Metabolism, Liver Enzymes, Taekwondo, Training

Resumen

Este estudio se llevó a cabo para determinar los cambios en las enzimas hepáticas y el metabolismo de los lípidos de los atletas después de un entrenamiento de taekwondo de diez semanas. El grupo de investigación está formado por 26 atletas masculinos que tienen licencia de taekwondo y participan en competiciones a nivel nacional. Al grupo de investigación se le aplicó un programa de entrenamiento para mejorar sus características condicionales con ejercicios de taekwondo de noventa minutos tres días a la semana durante diez semanas. Se tomaron muestras de sangre de los atletas dos veces en estado de reposo, al inicio y al final del entrenamiento. En las muestras tomadas al grupo de investigación se determinaron los niveles de enzimas hepáticas (ALP, AST, GGT, CRP, ALT, LDH), grasas en sangre (HDL, LDL, colesterol, triglicéridos), glucosa y urea. Los datos fueron analizados mediante el programa estadístico SPSS. Se aceptó el nivel de significancia como $p < 0,05$. Como resultado de la investigación, se observó que los valores de enzimas hepáticas, GGT y LDH de los deportistas aumentaron en los valores pre-post test, y hubo una disminución en los niveles de ALT, AST, ALP y PCR. Se determinó que los niveles de glucosa de los deportistas aumentaron en los valores pre-post test, y hubo una disminución en los valores pre-post test de los niveles de urea. Se observó que los valores pre-post test del nivel de HDL, que es uno de los parámetros del metabolismo lipídico del grupo de investigación, aumentaron, y los valores pre-post test de los niveles de colesterol, LDL y triglicéridos disminuyeron. En conclusión; Se observó que los entrenamientos de taekwondo de diez semanas provocaron cambios en los parámetros de las enzimas hepáticas, grasas en sangre, glucosa y urea de los atletas. De acuerdo con esta información, pensamos que, si los programas de entrenamiento se organizan considerando los períodos de competencia

de los atletas, afectará positivamente el rendimiento de los atletas.

Palabras clave: Metabolismo de Lípidos, Enzimas Hepáticas, Taekwondo, Entrenamiento

The health effects of training in physically active people are known, and it provides changes and improvements on cardiovascular capacity, skeletal-muscular system, body composition, lipid metabolism and liver enzymes in the organism. Physical exertion reduces mortality due to cardiovascular disease, ischemic heart disease and coronary artery disease in the body, besides being a therapeutic factor for the prevention of obesity and overweight, it is also important in terms of sportive performance¹ (Debnath et al., 2023). Especially regular and designed studies on a certain intensity affect physical and physiological parameters in athletes.

The rapid changes in technology, communication, technique and science experienced today directly or indirectly affect sports activities, sports science, as well as the social life and sports performance of the athlete² (Altınkök, 2015). The aim of all these innovative and modern developments is to combine all these developments with the training and to protect and develop the current sportive status of the athletes and to achieve new successes with the appropriate method³ (Erdoğan, 2020). Even if different activities and methods interact in order to achieve these goals, adequate and balanced nutrition, sleep patterns, adequate rest and up-to-date training methods can be provided to raise the athletes to the next level in terms of performance⁴ (Wax et al., 2021). Regular, different intensity and duration trainings create both physical and physiological effects on the body^{5,6} (Öztürk et al., 2022; Funes et al., 2011). Important markers of these physiological changes in the organism as a result of training are known as lipid metabolism together with liver enzymes. It is known that especially chronic exercises affect liver enzymes and lipid metabolism positively⁷ (Yao et al., 2018). Physiological aspects of long-term training in the organism; It is known that it causes some differences in muscle, cardiovascular system, body stockin levels, liver enzymes and lipid metabolism⁸ (Shin et al., 2016). Although it is known that training plays an active role in the regulation of liver enzymes and lipid metabolism; It is an important body organ that is effective in the regulation of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism and produces sufficient metabolites for the synthesis of muscle and brain tissue during high-intensity training⁹ (Shephard and Johnson, 2015). In line with this information, training and

the physiological state of the organism are extremely important in terms of sportive performance. The competitive environment that has developed in recent years, especially the sportive performance of the athletes in the competition and competition environment, and the physiological changes that will occur in the organism continue to attract the attention of researchers. In this research, it was carried out to determine the changes in the liver enzymes and lipid metabolism of the athletes of the regular taekwondo trainings.

Research Group

The research group consisted of 26 volunteer male athletes between the ages of 14-18, who are licensed in the taekwondo branch and regularly attend national and international competitions.

Training Program

A training program was applied to the research group to improve their conditional characteristics with ninety-minute taekwondo exercises three days a week for ten weeks. Within the scope of the training, 15-20 minutes of warm-up exercises, 50-60 minutes of taekwondo training and 10-minute cooling exercises were applied at the end of the training.

Biochemical Measurements

To the research group, 7 cc of blood was taken from the forearm elbow vein twice, before and after the training, by experts. The samples taken were analyzed in a private hospital laboratory and the liver enzymes (ALP, AST, GGT, CRP, ALT, LDH), blood fats (HDL, LDL, cholesterol, triglyceride), glucose and urea levels of the athletes were determined.

Analysis of Data

The analysis of the data was analyzed using the SPSS statistical package program. When the normality analysis of the data was evaluated, parametric tests were used in the analysis of the data determined to be normally distributed. "Paired Samples t" test was applied to compare the means of two independent groups and to test the significance between them. Significance was taken as $p < 0.05$.

Table 1. Biochemical Changes of Athletes Before and After Training

Parameters	Pre test	Post test	t	p
Glucose	90.08±1.32	93.12 ±2.08	-8.404	0.00*
Urea	12.19 ±2.80	10.54±2.26	2.336	0.02*
ALT	11.92±3.98	9.85±2.29	5.052	0.00*
AST	21.92±3.38	20.08±3.21	1.733	0.09
ALP	94.04±6.11	93.77±4.50	-1.342	0.19
GGT	14.58±1.39	14.92±1.76	-1.275	0.21
LDH	185.81±2.92	197.38±5.27	-15.636	0.00*
CRP	.54±.18	.51±.17	9.111	0.00*

*: p<0,05

When Table 1 was examined, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between the glucose, urea, ALT, LDH and CRP pre-post test values of the research group (p<0.05), while there was no significant difference between the AST, ALP and GGT pre-post test values. (p>0.05).

Table 2. Athletes' Pre- and Post-Training Lipid Metabolism Changes

Parameters	Pre test	Post test	t	p
HDL	52,50±4,35	53,65±3,81	-4,811	0,00*
LDL	57,42 ±6,73	55,77±5,65	4,550	0,00*
Triglyceride	68,35±3,81	67,19±3,76	7,500	0,00*
Cholesterol	98,38±7,56	96,65±6,41	2,613	0,01*

*: p<0,05

When Table 2 was evaluated, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between the HDL, LDL, cholesterol and triglyceride pre-posttest levels of the research group (p<0.05).

Regular and long-term training affects metabolic and cellular events in the organism and increases oxidative stress¹⁰. (Pillon Barcelos et al., 2017) This study was conducted to determine the effect of ten-week taekwondo training on the biochemical changes of athletes. It is known that long-term and high-intensity exercises affect the cellular metabolism of athletes as well as oxidative stress. In particular, liver enzymes and some biochemical parameters are important in terms of sportive performance,

as they are associated with many metabolic and physiological events^{11,12}. (Friedenreich et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). As a result of the trainings applied in the research, it was determined that there was an increase in glucose, GGT and LDH levels, and a decrease in the levels of urea, ALT, AST, ALP and CRP. When the studies are examined; Koçyiğit et al. (2011)¹³ stated in their study that vitamin C supplementation applied in addition to acute exercise affects the liver enzymes and plasma lipid levels of athletes, and that vitamin C supplementation to be taken in addition to the diet of athletes has beneficial effects on the cardiovascular system. Ekun et al., (2017)¹⁴ found in their study that there was an increase in liver enzymes and some biochemical parameters before and after the competition in athletes who regularly participate in football training. Sariakçalı et al., (2021), in their study, determined that a four-week practice training affected the participants' albumin, ALP, AST, CK, insulin, sedimentation and sodium parameters, and had a positive effect on lipid values, although not at a significant level. Bezci (2007) determined in his study that the training program he applied caused changes in the hematological, lipid and ALT and AST levels of the athletes. In a different study, Baydil et al. (2016) determined that short-term low altitude aerobic and technical training did not significantly affect the ALT, AST and CK parameters of the athletes. Mahdavi Asiabar et al. (2021)¹⁵, in their study, determined that a four-week practice training affected the participants' albumin, ALP, AST, CK, insulin, sedimentation and sodium parameters, and had a positive effect on lipid values, although not at a significant level. Bezci (2007)¹⁶ determined in his study that the training program he applied caused changes in the hematological, lipid and ALT and AST levels of the athletes. In a different study, Baydil et al. (2016)¹⁷ determined that short-term low altitude aerobic and technical training did not significantly affect the ALT, AST and CK parameters of the athletes. Mahdavi Asiabar et al. (2021)¹⁸, in their study, stated that four-week endurance training increased AST and ALT levels in exercise+placebo groups, and exercise and propolis consumption decreased liver damage. In his study, Erdoğan (2022)¹⁹ determined that regular volleyball training caused changes in the liver enzymes and muscle damage parameters of the athletes. Nobahar et al., (2020)²⁰ determined in their study that acute gradual exercise sessions increased the AST, ALT and ALP levels of the participants.

Salahshoor et al., (2014)²¹ stated in their study that omega-3 supplementation applied in addition to four-week high-intensity karate training can reduce the liver enzymes and muscle damage marker values of athletes.

Lipids are used as an energy source in the organism, and their excessive accumulation and increase is an indicator of the disease in the body, the problem as well as the negative impact on sportive performance (Moraes et al., 2017). According to the results of the research, it was determined that the trainings applied had a posi-

ve increase in the HDL values of the athletes, and a negative decrease in the LDL, cholesterol and triglyceride levels. When the studies are evaluated; In their study, Akin and Arıkan²² (2020) determined that eight-week endurance training affected the lipid metabolism of the participants and some biochemical parameters, and there was no change in irisin hormone levels. Koç and Tamer²³ (2008) stated in their study that eight-week aerobic and anaerobic training had a positive effect on the HDL, LDL and cholesterol levels of the participants. Erdoğan (2021)²⁴, in his study, determined that a regular and long-term training program for three months had a positive effect on the lipid metabolism and some biochemical parameters of the athletes. Lee et al., (2022)²⁵, in their study, determined that the acute taekwondo training program created changes in the lipid metabolism of the training program that the athletes applied in addition to the diet program. In their study, Devrilmez and Soslu (2022)²⁶ stated that eight-week repetitive running training had a positive effect on athletes' muscle damage, liver enzymes, lipid metabolism and kidney functions. In their study, Sagarkar et al. (2020)²⁷ determined that the athletes who applied an acute exercise program had significant changes in lipid metabolism. Bülbül et al. (2022)²⁸ stated that the ten-week training program had a significant effect on the lipid metabolism and hematological parameters of the athletes.

In conclusion; It was observed that ten-week taekwondo trainings caused changes in the liver enzymes (ALP, AST, GGT, CRP, ALT, LDH), blood fats (HDL, LDL, cholesterol, triglyceride), glucose and urea parameters of the athletes. In line with this information, we think that if training programs are organized considering the competition periods of the athletes, it will positively affect the performance of the athletes.

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